

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT
GPR	11	B		Min: 62.917 Max: 63.180	1423 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic

In cross-section? Yes No In elevation drawing? Yes No Photos: Yes No #: 1344-1447 Photo Model: Yes No #:

DEFINITION: *greenish silt abutting SU 1386*

Covered by SU: 1386 Fills SU: Filled by SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? Color Composition Compaction

FORMATION PROCESS: Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are

Anthropic	Geological	Organic	SOIL/MATRIX				
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery M <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tiles R <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Dolia R <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) f (small) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone R (small) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Basalt f (small) <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Charcoal R <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal bones M <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth R <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	clay 40% silt 60% sand 0% <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive <table border="1"> <tr> <th>Compaction</th> <th>Color</th> </tr> <tr> <td> <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft </td> <td> <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) <i>Greenish-brown</i> </td> </tr> </table>	Compaction	Color	<input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft	<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) <i>Greenish-brown</i>
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UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit Depth: Original Not Original

Southern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Western Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Eastern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by: 1386, 1383	Abuts:
Is covered by: 1327	Covers: 1184
Is cut by: 1347, Marcia, Shubie	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS: *excavated w. trowel + pick, dry conditions*

DESCRIPTION

Position within sector: *South-central*

Shape: *two rectangles connected by a narrow strip*

For layers complete this section:

Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): *flat*

Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): *Tufo + basalt rubble clusters s. of wall SU 1383*

Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): *extends to bedrock in N. section, overlies remains of tufo floor in S-W*

Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commigled other (specify)

- = SU 1423
- = SU 1184
- = SU 1386

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

Dark, silty deposit overlying bedrock and sections of wall 1184. It appears to naturally abutt SO1386 which is separated by an irregular rubble fall along the southern edge of 1423. Presumably 1423 represents a natural deposition prior to the deposition of SO1386 to the south. 1423 may be contemporary to SO 1428 to the west, but appears distinct based on soil composition.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets): 1

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size: n.a.

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by T. Hart

on 21/7/11

Revised by CMH

on 26/7/11

PDFd by ECR

on 28/7/11

Entered by

on